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Research Article

Prevention and management of occupational sharp injuries among health care workers at secondary care hospitals in Sri Lanka

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ABSTRACT

Health care workers are at risk of exposure to infections like Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C and Human Immunodeficiency Virus and other blood-borne pathogens due to accidental exposure to contaminated sharp objects. The objective of this study was to improve the knowledge and practices among health care workers on management and prevention of occupational sharps injuries at secondary care hospitals in Galle district, Sri Lanka. Validated questionnaires, key informant interviews and checklists were developed to determine the existing system and current Knowledge and practices among health care workers. A training programme with the multimodal interventions was developed to address the gaps in the knowledge, practice, and existing system. Health care workers (n=139) were included in this project. The study was conducted as three components. Post-test sample was compared with pre-test sample by using paired t-test. The level of knowledge was significantly increased among nursing officers ($p < 0.05$) and health care assistants ($p < 0.05$), but not among medical officers. The level of practices was significantly improved in all health care workers in the post-test sample ($p < 0.05$). The participants checked for Hepatitis B antibody level ($p < 0.05$) and the number immune to Hepatitis B ($p < 0.05$) was increased significantly after intervention. According to the qualitative part of the study, the overall mechanism available to manage and prevention of OSIs at those institutions was also improved after the intervention. The results show the ability to improve the knowledge and practices on occupational sharp injuries among health care workers by planned training and improve the system through a multimodal approach.

Keywords: Occupational sharp injuries, health care workers, training program, knowledge, and practices

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INTRODUCTION

A sharps injury is a penetrating stab wound from a needle, scalpel, or other sharp objects that may result in exposure to blood or other body fluids (1). Health Care Workers (HCW) work in close contact with infected patients are at risk of exposure to blood-borne infections due to accidental exposure to contaminated sharps objects. Hepatitis B and C viruses and HIV are the most commonly transmitted pathogens to HCW in an occupational settings (2). Additionally, 20 different pathogens such as Tuberculosis, Diphtheria, Herpes, malaria, Ebola virus infection and Epstein-bar virus infection are transmitted by infected body fluids (3).

Occupational sharps injuries within HCW can happen at any stage, during their use, transfer, disassembly, or disposal. Apart from the equipment design, the nature of the procedure, working conditions and staff experience are also mentioned as influencing factors for sharp injuries (4). In 2007, the world health organization (WHO) estimated that global sharps injuries among HCWs were around two million per year.

Annually 5.9%, 2.6%, and 0.5% of HCWs are exposed to HBV, HCV and HIV respectively. WHO further estimated that 40% to 70% of stick injuries around the world are underreported (5).

There is no national surveillance data regarding occupational exposure to blood and body fluids in Sri Lanka. According to past surveys conducted in specific institutions, average of 9.5% and 4.3% of health care workers had exposed to needle stick and cut injuries respectively (6). Implementation of preventive strategies such as immunization against HBV, mechanisms to prevent percutaneous injuries and post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) should be included in any health facility.

WHO estimated that 40% to 70% of OSI around the world are underreported (5). There were approximately 16000 HCV infections, 66000 cases of HBV infections and 1000 cases of HIV infections caused by OSI annually among HCW worldwide. The majority of these cases were reported from the developing countries (7). OSI can happen at any stage, during their use, transfer, disassemble or disposal. Apart from the equipment design, the nature of the procedure, working conditions and staff experience are also mentioned as influencing factors for sharp injuries (4).

National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health revealed that 50% of all OSI were not reported (8). It also highlighted “knowledge of needle stick and sharps injuries needs to be improved” among HCWs. Employees who work with sharps, require proper education and training on handling the sharps as part of a sharp’s injury prevention program. HCWS should be trained to protect themselves and others, while usage of sharps and after the procedure (9).

Standard precaution is a well-known prevention approach with demonstrated effectiveness in preventing exposure to blood and body fluid (10). However, it focuses mainly on the use of barrier methods (PPE) and work-practice controls (e.g., care in handling sharp devices). The manual of “Global burden of disease” series 3 indicated, vaccinating HCW as early as possible in their career against hepatitis B is as good preventive measure. It is also advised to immunizing against HBV as a highly efficacious post-exposure prophylaxis measure. It explained the decline of HIV markedly (58 to 10) in industrialized countries due to use of the PEP (11).

Around 40% - 65% HBV and HCV infections among HCWs were attributable to percutaneous exposure in developing countries. By contrast, it is reduced to 8% - 27% for HCV and less than 10% for HBV in developed countries due to the existence of good management and prevention system (7). Incidence of these injuries can be reduced markedly through strict adherence to universal safety precautions and identifying and managing risk factors. Sri Lankan study revealed that knowledge on immediate management of the wound after exposure is relatively low among HCWs and suggest conducting in service training on infection control for the HCWs, to update knowledge on post exposure management (6). According to the past Sri Lankan studies MOs are the most vulnerable category among HCWs to OSI (12).

Background

According to the findings of a study conducted in base hospitals of Kalutara District, there was a 63.4% prevalence and 29.4% incidence rate of sharps injuries among medical officers. About 34.5% of exposed participants had ignored the exposure. Only 38.7% reported the incident and obtained the necessary action (13). A study conducted in Galle and Kalutara Districts in 2016 revealed that the mechanism available to management and prevention for occupational injuries was not satisfactory and these occupational sharp injuries (OSI) were not reported (14).

OSIs imposed direct cost to the health system for post-exposure medical treatments and indirect cost as disability and absenteeism of the injured HCW. It also influences the quality of life of the HCW and causes greater anxiety and fear for individuals and families. To prevent those outcomes, it is essential to have a good system to manage and prevent OSI and HCWs should have better knowledge and practices. The current system established to manage and prevent OSI at Galle District is not satisfactory. Although some institutions have established mechanisms, the quality and comprehensiveness of these may not be satisfactory.

The objective of this study was to improve the knowledge and practices among health care workers on management and prevention of occupational sharps injuries at secondary care hospitals in Galle District, Sri Lanka.

METHODOLOGY

This Interventional study was designed to improve the prevention and management of OSI among HCW at secondary care hospitals in the Galle district from 1st of August 2018 to 15th of June 2019. The project contained three components.

The existing system for management, prevention of OSI was assessed by using a checklist, observations and conducting KIIs with medical superintendents (3), consultant microbiologist, ICNOs (3), matrons (3), overseers (3) and ward sisters/in charges (12) at the 3 secondary care hospitals and the current level of knowledge and practices on management and prevention of OSI among HCW was assessed by using a self-administered questionnaire. HCW (medical officers, nurses and health care assistants) who have been working for more than 1 year at BHs in Galle district were included. The key informant interviews guides were designed to gather data on weaknesses in the service delivery and suggestions for improvement. The deficiencies pointed out by the participants were prioritized and those were considered for developing the intervention. The responses of key informants were recorded, and thematic analysis was carried out. A purposive sampling technique was used to find the members for KII.

Direct observations of service delivery were made by trained investigators at randomly selected time slots with the objective of triangulation of data gathered from key informants' interviews. The observation was conducted for random 21 days from 8 am to 8 pm. Observers were trained by principal investigator prior to the study.

Sample size (n) was calculated by using Lwanga and Lemeshow's (1991) formula for population prevalence 0.1 (since the previous studies were done in a similar setting this was taken as 0.1), precision 0.05 and confidence level 95%. Sample size (n) = $\frac{1.96^2 \times 0.0.1(1-0.1)}{0.05^2} = 138.24 \sim 139$.

Hence, the required sample size was 139. The stratified random sampling technique was used. Sample of HCWs from three categories (medical officers, nursing officers, health care assistants) was selected according to the number of workers in each category. The same principle was adapted to all three hospitals. Attendance registers were used as the sampling frames for NO and HCA. A list of personal file numbers was used as sampling frame for MO. (25 MOs, 56 NOs and 58 HCAs were included in the project).

Questionnaire was developed by reviewing the literature on previous surveys and referring the "workbook for designing, implementing and evaluating a sharps injury prevention programme" of CDC, United States (4). International and local literature was referred during the preparation of questionnaire, and it was prepared after detailed discussions with supervisor, experts in Microbiology and Public health. Then it was validated by expert opinion (for content validity) and in the field level staff and supervisor (face validity). The questionnaire included to assess general information such as date, place of interview, parameters such as age, sex, service and current working unit, knowledge on diseases which can be transmitted via percutaneous exposure, practices and immunization status for hepatitis B, information about exposure and post exposure response to sharps injuries.

C1, C2, C6, D4, D6 questions were used to calculate the knowledge score. Marks were ranged from 0 to 25 and the cut of value was set at 18.75 (75th percentile). Marks above this cut-off value were considered satisfactory. C3, C5, C7 questions were used to assess the overall practice. The range of marks was 0 to 15 and the cut off value was set at 11.25 (75th percentile). Those who obtained marks higher than this level consider as satisfactory.

The questionnaire was pre-tested among 25 HCWs at BH Horana. The questionnaire was adjusted according to the findings of the pre-test. The Multimodal intervention was designed and implemented to improve the management and prevention of OSI. Training programs were conducted to improve the knowledge and practices on management, prevention, and reporting of OSI. Training sessions were conducted by a consultant microbiologist and experts in relevant fields with lectures, video clips and discussions. Basic knowledge on Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C and HIV, knowledge on standard precautions and safety disposal of clinical waste, knowledge on post exposure response, prophylaxis and reporting were included in the training programs. Two wall charts were developed and displayed in wards on prevention and the correct post exposure response (management) following OSI. These charts were developed according to ministry circular (15), guidelines of the college of microbiologists (16) and standard

precautions (11). The working environment in wards was arranged to prevent the OSI. Facilities for prevention and management of OSI were also improved at the ward and institutional levels. Hepatitis B vaccination coverage among HCWs was improved. As screening for hepatitis B antibodies at MRI takes a long time, discussed with the Virologist at TH Karapitiya and 50 blood samples were screened per week.

Post-interventional improvement of the system for management, prevention of OSI was assessed by using the checklist, observations and KII and post-interventional improvement in knowledge and practices among HCW was assessed by using same questionnaire by using the same samples as in pre intervention. SPSS statistical software was used to analyze the quantitative data. Appropriate statistical tests were performed to assess the significance. Statistical significance of pre and post interventional differences was tested by using paired t-test. Qualitative data were thematically analyzed after coding them and grouping them into common thematic areas.

RESULTS

This interventional research project was conducted at secondary care hospitals in the Galle District from 01.01.2019 to 30.06.2019 to improve the management and prevention of OSI among HCWs. Both, qualitative as well as the quantitative components, were included in this project. Most of the study participants were in 30-39 and 40- 49 years age groups (33.1% each). The majorities were females (72.7%) and had more than 10 years of working experience (39.6%).

Pre interventional stage

Accessibility to sharp bins (57%), availability of different sized gloves (32%) was not satisfied before the intervention. There was no adequate working space (68%) and poor lighting (65%) in most of the wards. Reporting forms were not available at most of the wards (91%) and guidelines on prevention (73%) and post-exposure management (81%) were not displayed satisfactorily in the majority. Overall knowledge on OSI revealed that, among the study participants, 52% of the MO and 21.4% NO had satisfactory knowledge. Overall knowledge among HCA was very low (3.4%) in the pre-test sample (Table I).

Table I: Impact of intervention on overall knowledge on prevention and management of OSI

Parameter - Overall knowledge on sharps injuries					
	Pre test		Post test		Significance t-test, p value
	Number	%	Number	%	
Medical officers					
Satisfactory	13	52	21	84	t = - 2.55
Not satisfactory	12	48	04	16	p= 0.17
Nursing officers					
Satisfactory	12	21.4	24	42.9	t = - 4.106
Not satisfactory	44	78.6	32	57.1	p = <0.05
HCA					
Satisfactory	02	3.4	21	36.2	t = - 5.230
Not satisfactory	57	96.6	37	63.8	p = <0.05

Overall practices on prevention and management of OSI among HCWs revealed that only 44% of MO and 41.1% of NOs were satisfactory practices. Practices among HCA were further low with a 15.5% satisfactory rate (Table II).

Table II: Impact of intervention on overall Practice on prevention and management of OSI

Parameter - Overall practice on OSI					
	Pre- test		Post-test		Significance t-test, p value
	Number	%	Number	%	
Medical officers					
Satisfactory	11	44	20	80.0	t = - 3.133
Not satisfactory	14	56	5	20.0	p = .005
Nursing officers					
Satisfactory	23	41.1	42	75.0	p = .000
Not satisfactory	33	58.9	14	25.0	t = - 4.730
HCA					
Satisfactory	09	15.5	29	50.0	p = .000
Not satisfactory	49	84.5	29	50.0	t = - 4.798

The majority (92.1%) was taken at least 1 dose of vaccine for Hepatitis B and 62.6% of participants completed all three doses of vaccine. Among vaccinated participants, only 46.8% had checked the antibody levels. Only 25.2% had enough antibody level against Hepatitis B. (Table III).

Table III: Impact on intervention on status of immunization for Hepatitis B in study population

	Pre-test		Post-test		Significance t-test, P value
	Number	Percentage (%)	Number	Percentage (%)	
Vaccinated for Hepatitis B					
Yes	128	92.1	133	95.7	t = 1.908, P= 0.059
No	11	7.9	6	4.3	
Completed all three doses of vaccine					
Yes	87	62.6	101	72.7	t = 1.551, P= 0.123
No	52	37.4	38	27.3	
Checked antibody level following vaccination					
Yes	65	46.8	93	66.9	t = 3.505, P= 0.001
No	74	53.2	46	33.1	
Immune for Hepatitis B					
Yes	35	25.2	78	56.1	t = 7.394, P= 0.000
No	18	12.9	15	10.8	
Don't know	86	61.9	46	33.1	

It was stated that 45.3% of HCWs in the study population had been exposed to OSI during their career. Most (34.0%) were exposed during drawing blood or giving injection by own. The careless practice was perceived as the cause for the exposure by the majority of participants (55.5%). The majority of not reporting participants (49.2%) assumed the incident as not harmful (Table IV).

Table IV: Distribution of exposure status to sharp injury among study population (Pre - test)

	Number	Percentage (%)
Exposure status		
Exposed	63	45.3
Not exposed	76	54.7
Way of exposure to OSI		
While giving injection/drawing blood	22	34.0
Due to improperly discarded sharps	15	23.0
While doing procedure	15	23.0
While assisting	06	9.5
While recapping	05	7.9
Causes for OSI		
Your careless practice	35	55.5
Incorporate patient	22	34.0
Congested working environment	05	7.9
Improper lighting	01	1.5
Reasons for not to follow up after exposure		
Thought as Harmless	31	49.2
High workload	08	12.6
Not aware of safety measures	08	12.6
Organization culture not facilitate follow up	08	12.6
Emergency	05	7.9
Senior not willing to stop the procedure	03	4.7

Post-interventional stage

The same checklist used in the pre-interventional stage was used to describe the improvement in infrastructure facilities in the 3 institutions after the intervention. Accessibility to sharp bins (82%), availability of different sized gloves (83%) was satisfactory after the intervention. There was no improvement in working space (65%) and a slight improvement in lightings (77%). Reporting forms were available in all wards of all three health care institutions and guidelines on prevention (86%) and post-exposure management (94%) were displayed satisfactorily.

Knowledge score on OSI among all HCWs was improved in the post-test sample. Among the study participants, MOs obtained the highest score with 84%, 42.9% NOs and 36.2% HCA also reached the satisfactory level (Table 1).

In the post-test sample, 80% of MO, 75% of NO and 50% HCA reached to a satisfactory level of overall practices on OSI (Table II).

The majorities (95.7%) of participants were taken at least 1 dose of the Hepatitis B vaccine in the post-test sample and 72.7% of participants completed all three doses. Among vaccinated, 66.9% had checked the antibody levels. In the post-test sample, 56.1% had enough antibody level against Hepatitis B (Table III).

The impact of the intervention on management and prevention of OSI at Galle District was assessed by comparing the pre and post-test values for overall knowledge, practices and status of immunization for Hepatitis B by using paired t-test. Overall level of knowledge was increased significantly among NO ($t = -4.106$, $p = <0.05$) and HCA ($t = -5.230$, $p = <0.05$) in post-test sample. Although there is an increase in the level of knowledge among MO after the intervention, it was not significant (Table I).

Overall practice on OSI was significantly increased among MO ($t = -3.133$, $p = .005$), NO ($t = -4.730$, $p = .000$) and HCA ($t = -4.798$, $p = .000$) after intervention (Table II).

In the post-test sample, vaccination for hepatitis B and those who completed all 3 doses of vaccine were increased but this was not significant. The participants checked for antibody level ($t = 3.505$, $P = 0.001$) and number immune to hepatitis B ($t = 7.394$, $P = 0.000$) were increased significantly after intervention (Table III).

DISCUSSION

This research project was designed to improve the mechanism for management and prevention of occupational sharps injuries among health care workers in the Galle District.

In the pre-test sample, 52% of the MO had satisfactory knowledge of OSI. These findings were aligned to findings (55.8%) of the study conducted in the Kalutara District (13) and similar findings were also explained by Karawita *et al.* (6). Knowledge among NO and health care assistant was not satisfactory in pre-test sample. Better overall training during medical faculty and high technical knowledge of doctors may be the reason for the difference among these groups. Overall practices to prevent OSI were not satisfactory among all three groups in the pre-test sample. Although, a study conducted among NOs in Egypt reveals that overall practice was good among NO (17).

In the pre-test sample, the majority of HCWs obtained the vaccine for Hepatitis B (92.1%). These findings were similar to the results of a study conducted in Pakistan (18) and in Kalutara district (13) in which 90.9% and 97.4% HCWs were vaccinated for Hepatitis B respectively. Among the vaccinated group, only 46.8% HCWs were checked for the antibody level. Only a few of them (25.2%) had satisfactory antibody levels against Hepatitis B but improved following the intervention.

Most (45.3%) of HCWs had been exposed to OSI at least once during their career. Drawing blood or giving injection by own attributes to 34% of the exposed cases. Own careless practice (55.5%) was the major cause for the OSI. Majority of "not reporting" participants (49.2%) assumed the incident as "not harmful". These figures are similar to a study conducted in Kalutara district (13) but different from a study conducted in Iran (Prevalence of NSI was 76.1%) (19).

The level of knowledge was increased significantly among NO and HCA in the post-test sample. Correct practices on handling sharps were also significantly increased among all three groups after intervention. It indicated that planned training programmes displaying the guidelines at the workplace would improve the level of knowledge and practices on OSI among HCWs.

The participants checked for antibody level and the number immune to Hepatitis B were significantly increased in post-test. Increased awareness through training and displaying guidelines and deciding to send the screening sample to THK would be the reason for this rise.

CONCLUSION

This research project was carried out to improve the system for prevention and management of OSI at base hospitals in the Galle District. The overall level of knowledge and practices on prevention and management

of OSI among health care workers and the system for management and prevention of OSI was not satisfied before the intervention. The vaccination status for Hepatitis B was also not satisfactory.

Following the intervention, the overall level of knowledge and practices on prevention and management of OSI was improved and the working environment and facilities at the institutional level were improved. Vaccination status for hepatitis B was also improved. Based on the findings of this research project, the following recommendations can be made.

1. It is important to arrange facilities to obtain 100% immunization coverage for HBV, since there is a proportion of HCWs without the immunity for Hepatitis B,
2. Highly recommend using simple and cheap methods like demonstration and illustration of safety and post-exposure guidelines on blood and body fluid exposure, in relevant places of the work area, which can help to reduce the exposure and enhance the post exposure reporting.
3. Past studies explain that availability of resources and post-exposure programs do not guarantee to adherence to protective measures, PEP and follow-up of health care workers on percutaneous exposure. To overcome these condition hospital administrators and the infection control teams should build a safety culture within the premises, wherein everyone commits to personal responsibility for safety and to adopt safe practices.

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Ethical approval

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